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Background & Significance

- Burnout is a significant problem in the U.S. with a considerable role in why nurses are leaving the workforce (Shah et al., 2021)
- Burnout is defined as a state of continuous psychological stress within work life and has an influential negative impact on patients, the workforce, and organizations (Kelly & Adams, 2018)
- For clinical nurses at the bedside burnout is well studied, but there is growing concern for the much less studied burnout of nurse leaders (Prochnow et al., 2021)

Problem Statement

- Burnout is reported by registered nurses across a variety of practice settings, at all levels of nursing nationwide (Peacock, 2023)
- There is limited literature examining burnout rates and factors contributing to burnout among nurse leaders (Shah et al., 2021)

Project Purpose

- The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to create a nurse leader burnout mitigation toolkit at a local community, Magnet®-recognized hospital
- A pre- and post-toolkit implementation survey was utilized to measure the efficacy of the toolkit

Supporting Framework - PARIHS

Methodology

- This DNP project utilized the PARIHS framework to guide the enculturation of an evidenced-based burnout mitigation toolkit. The implementation of a nurse leader mitigation burnout toolkit included a validated assessment tool, comprehensive education, workplace adjustments, and evaluation (Shanafelt & Noseworthy, 2017)
- The Oldenburg Burnout Inventory is a self-report assessment survey designed to measure burnout in the workplace. The survey is intended to measure physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion experienced in relation to work (Pate et al., 2023)
- Education and training equipped nurse leaders with knowledge and skills enabling them to identify symptoms, manage stress, and foster well-being to mitigate burnout

Results

- The sample included 24 nurse leaders that completed the pre-survey and education sessions, a participation rate of 96% among eligible nurse leaders
- One participant resigned during the project; 22 completed the post-survey

Question	Pre-survey Mean (N=24)	Post-survey Mean (N=22)	P value
This is the only type of work I can imagine myself doing.	3.13	3.77	.042
After working, I have enough energy for my leisure activities.	2.63	3.23	.091
I feel more and more engaged in my work.	3.58	3.91	.106
I find my work to be a positive challenge.	4.04	4.23	.117

Discussion

- Findings demonstrate the extent of burnout among nurse leaders and show promising results from the use of the toolkit
- Aspects of nurse leaders' work, such as incorporating innovative practices, professional development opportunities, or engaging in meaningful wellness activities, support nurse leader well-being and help to mitigate nurse leader burnout
- Health systems must focus on implementing strategies to alleviate nurse leader burnout as part of an effort to create a healthy work environment

Limitations & Recommendations

- The abbreviated timeframe for implementation and utilization of the toolkit may have impacted findings
- Further strategies should be developed and studied to determine their impact on mitigating burnout in nurse leaders
- Longitudinal tracking of nurse leader turnover is needed to determine the efficacy of the toolkit

References

